

Study of single point incremental forming limits of Al 1050/Mg-AZ31B two-layer sheets fabricated by roll bonding technique: Finite element simulation and experiment

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Forming limited diagram
Incremental forming
Finite element simulation
Roll bonding process
Mechanical properties
Design of experiment

ABSTRACT

In this work, for the first time, the two-layer Aluminum (Al 1050) and magnesium (AZ31B) sheet were used in the single point incremental forming (SPIF) process. Due to the high strength-to-weight ratio of the Al 1050/Mg-AZ31B sample, today it is used in significant industries such as automotive and aerospace. The finite element simulation process was carried out using the Abaqus Software considering five approaches to determine forming limits. These approaches were forming limit diagram criterion (FLD_{crt}), effective strain rate (ESR), second derivation of thinning (SDT), Major strain rate (MSR) and Thickness strain rate (TSR) methods. The results showed that the failure prediction in the FLD_{crt} method was more accurate than other methods. The thickness distribution process was carried out both by simulation and experiment to validate the simulation results. The results show a good agreement between simulation and experimental results. Finally, the results obtained from the SPIF process were compared with the FLD results of the conventional hemispherical punch test, and it was observed that the FLD was higher in the SPIF process. Moreover, the layer arrangement, which affects formability, was investigated. The results showed that the FLD with Mg-AZ31B/Al 1050 arrangement fails in higher strains compared to Al 1050/Mg-AZ31B. After validating the simulation results, the parameter effect of the step-down and tool diameter on the two-layer formability was investigated by the design of experiment. Considering the greater importance of the step-down and tool diameter effect on the created stresses and forming time compared to other parameters, their effect will be investigated. The results showed an optimal condition for the tool diameter, but an opposite relationship with formability was obtained for the step-down.

1. Introduction

The production and use of composite sheets are increasing due to their properties. Lightweight composites, including Al and Mg, are used in various automotive, aerospace, and military industries. One of the advantages of composite samples is combining different mechanical, physical and chemical properties of two or more base sheets simultaneously [1]. Due to the importance of investigating the formability of composite samples, researchers are interested in studying the formability of composite samples. Traditional methods to obtain the FLD can refer to the deep drawing process or methods such as the Erickson or Nakajima test. Recently, according to the advantages of the SPIF process, studies have been conducted to investigate the composite formability of the SPIF [2].

Nie et al. [3] investigated the effect of temperature on the formability of the three-layer Al/Mg/Al sheet by the deep drawing process. They

reported that formability increased with increasing temperature. Rahmatabadi et al. [4] employed two methods, namely Nakajima and ultrasonic vibration test, in order to examine the FLD diagram of the Al/Mg two-layer sheet. They reported that the FLD in ultrasonic vibration is higher than with the conventional method. Delshad et al. [5] investigated the effect of annealing temperature on the formability of the Br/St14/Br 3-layer sheet. They showed that increasing the annealing temperature will decrease the strength and hardness while increasing the formability. Jalali et al. [6] studied the FLD for Al/Br two-layer samples by the SPIF process experimentally and numerically. They show that FLD for Br/Al arrangement was more suitable than Al/Br arrangement. The maximum second derivative of the equivalent method in their simulation process was used to study FLD.

Zaba et al. [7] investigated the effect of the step-down on formability and thickness distribution value in the SPIF for Cu/Al sheet. This study

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2024.01.085>

Received 24 September 2023; Received in revised form 8 January 2024; Accepted 10 January 2024

Available online 11 January 2024

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Table 1

The chemical composition of raw materials in terms of weight percentage (wt.%).

	Al	Sb	Ni	Mg	Zn	Fe	Cu	Si	Mn
Al1050	99/8	0/02	0/003	0/005	0/196	0/472	0/095	0/096	0
Mg AZ31B	2.45	0	0	97/36	0/294	0/004	0	0/049	0/186

Fig. 1. SPIF equipment for experimental test.

showed that the formability increases by increasing the step-down up to 1.1. Hasan et al. [8] investigated the formability of a two-layer steel/steel sheet by the SPIF process. They found that in the rolling process, the formability decreases with the increase in the thickness reduction percentage. They investigated the effect of the parameters of the SPIF process on the ductility of the two-layer sheets. They showed that the formability decreases with the increase of the tool diameter. Ashouri et al. [9] investigated the effect of the parameters in the SPIF process on the formability of the two-layer Br/St13 sheet. They showed that the formability decreases with the tool diameter and feed rate increase. Ali et al. [10] investigated the effect of arrangement for a layer of two SUS/Al layers and found that the formability increases in the arrangement with the external Al layer. Harhash et al. [11] studied fracture forming limit and forming limit curve for 3-layer Steel/polymer/Steel samples with the help of the SPIF method with three geometries, cone with variable and fixed angle, semi-spherical and multi-stage forming and showed that with multi-stage forming method, it is possible to consider taking the small wall angles at each stage to increase formability. Khalid et al. [12] investigated the formability of the two-layer sheet by 2 SPIF and stamping methods, and it was found that the formability in the SPIF method is higher than the stamping method. Ghamdi and Hussain [13] investigated the effect of annealing on the formability of a two-layer Cu/steel sheet by the SPIF method. They showed that with an annealing temperature of up to 700°, the

formability would be increased by about 10 %. Esmailian et al. [14] investigated the effect of SPIF parameters on the formability of 3-layer sheet by surface response method (RSM) and reported the optimal parameters to increase formability. Karajibani et al. [15] determined FLD for the two-layer copper/aluminum sheets. The work was carried out experimentally and numerically with the Nakajima test method. They used second-order derivatives equivalent plastic strain and major strain criterion in the numerical approach. They reported that the numerical approach is more accurate in predicting the necking location than the experimental data. Samir et al. [16] used the Gurson-Tvergaard-Needleman (GTN) method to predict failure in the SPIF process and reported that the results are in good agreement with the experimental method. They used the Response Surface Method (RSM) to obtain the optimal parameters of the GTN method. A numerical study was done to predict the FLD in the SPIF process with the help of fracture criteria, including the ductile fracture criteria [17], the Hill criterion, as well as meridional and triaxiality stress [18].

According to the conducted studies, it was observed that the investigation of the formability for the two-layer Al 1050/Mg AZ31B sheets fabricated by cold rolling process, with SPIF process in the form of numerical and experimental studies had yet to be done. Due to the increasing use of sheets with a high strength-to-weight ratio and the industrial uses of the SPIF process, the need to investigate the formability of Al/Mg sheets by the SPIF process will become necessary.

Fig. 2. (a) Sample size according to ASTM-E8M, (b) tensile test sample.

Fig. 3. Extrapolation of the true stress-strain curve Base and Rolled sample.

Table 2

N and k parameters are obtained from the Hollomon equation.

Sample	n	K (MPa)
Rolled Al	0.119	185
Rolled Mg	0.115	448
Base Al	0.251	128
Base Mg	0.032	618

Therefore, in this article, the study of the FLD for the Al/Mg sample was investigated numerically and experimentally by the SPIF process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

The substrates used in this study were AZ31B (Mg–3Al–1Zn, wt. %) magnesium and Al 1050 with thicknesses of 1 and 2 mm, respectively.

Fig. 4. (a). Placement of tool, sheets, and Die relative to each other, (b) Preparing a two-layersample for simulation.

Fig. 5. (a). Variable angle geometry, (b) Spiral tool path with cone and pyramid geometry.

The chemical compositions of the base metals are shown in Table 1. Quantometric test method was used to analyze the chemical composition of Al 1050 and Mg AZ31B. The samples were cut with 135 mm and 75 mm length and width, respectively. After the cold roll bonding process with 50 % strain, the dimensions of the two-layer samples will be 130 × 130 mm.

2.2. Incremental forming

The SPIF process investigated the formability of two-layer sheets. SPIF was carried out using a CNC milling machine equipped with a specially designed spherical head tool with a diameter of 14 mm and with the fixture shown in Fig. 1. The tool path used in the experimental forming was generated by the Power-Mill CAM software with spiral path and step-down of 0.5 mm, so that the rotation speed and the feed rate

were 500 rpm and 1200 mm/min, respectively. One of the reasons for choosing a spiral tool path is its greater malleability compared to other common tool paths [19].

2.3. Tensile test

A tensile test was carried out according to the ASTM-E8M standard to obtain the mechanical properties. The tensile test sample was cut with the sub-size using the laser cut. Fig. 2 shows the dimension of the sample size and some of the prepared tensile test specimens. A 5-ton tensile device carried out the tensile test, and the speed of the test was 2 mm/min.

Since in the process of SPIF, failure occurs at higher strains than with other conventional processes; it is necessary for FEM to continue the tensile test results up to strain 1 (Fig. 3). The true stress-strain diagram

Fig. 6. Two-layer sheet with Mg/Al arranged. (a) Cone geometric, (b) pyramid geometric.

Fig. 7. 2-layer sheet with Al/Mg arranged with cone geometric.

Fig. 8. SPIF for Base sheets, (a) Al sheet, (b) Mg sheet.

Fig. 9. FLD of SPIF process, (a) Al and Mg base sheets, (b) Mg/Al with cone and pyramid geometric, (c) Al/Mg with cone geometric.

Table 3

The results obtained from the SPIF process for the two-layersheet

Sample	Depth forming (mm)	Forming Limit Angel (degree)	Major Strain(ϵ_1)	Minor Strain(ϵ_2)
Mg/Al (Cone)	9	37	0.199	0.049
Mg/Al (pyramid)	8.5	35	0.15	0.0493
Al/Mg (cone)	5	30.5	0.081	0.013
Al base	47.6	69	0.51	0.083
Mg base	7.7	34	0.111	0.064

Fig. 10. Thickness distribution of cone geometric, (a) Base Mg,(b) Comparison of experimental, numerical for thickness distribution up to 7.7°, (c) Base AL (d) Comparison of experimental, numerical for thickness distribution up to 47.6°.

Fig. 11. Thickness distribution of cone geometric with Mg/Al arrangement, (a) Al layer,(b) Mg layer,(c) Comparison of experimental, numerical for thickness distribution up to 37°.

Fig. 12. Thickness distribution of pyramid geometric with Mg/Al arrangement, (a) Al layer,(b) thickness distribution for corner zone(c) Mg layer,(d) Comparison of experimental, numerical for thickness distribution up to 35°.

Fig. 13. Thickness distribution of cone geometric with Al/Mg arrangement, (a) Al layer,(b) Mg layer,(c) Comparison of experimental, numerical for thickness distribution up to 30.5°.

Table 4

The results obtained for thickness distribution.

Sample	Exp Average (mm)	Sim Average (mm)	Error (%)
Mg/Al (Cone)	1.4	1.34	5
Mg/Al (pyramid)	1.41	1.38	3
Al/Mg (cone)	1.5	1.4	7
Al base	1.50	1.68	12
Mg base	0.85	0.93	9.5

should be extrapolated by the Hollomon equation by obtaining the constant coefficients N and K according to equation (1). The results of the base and rolled sheets are shown in Table 2.

$$\sigma = K\varepsilon^n \quad (1)$$

2.4. Finite element model

For the numerical simulation of the SPIF process, the commercial ABAQUS/Explicit finite element modelling (FEM) software is utilized. The specifications of the CPU used in the simulation process are Intel Core i7-11700 Processor. Six multiple processors were used to increase the speed of analysis in the ABAQUS software. The simulation process is in accordance with the experimental test, the spherical head tool with a 14 mm diameter is taken into account, and the die is considered the analytical rigid component without the need for analysis and meshing. Due to the two-layer status of the sample, the Al and Mg layers were considered separately and are simulated as a deformable shell planer component. After this, they were considered as two layers with a tie constraint. Fig. 4 shows the setup of the simulation. The elastic and plastic properties used for the sheet are adopted from the Von-Misses yield criterion. Considering that the two-layer sheets are produced under the rolling process, the properties of each layer are considered separately in accordance with the effect of cold working resulting from the rolling process. For this purpose, Al and Mg sheets were rolled in a single layer, and then the properties obtained from the tensile test according to Table 2 and Fig. 3 were considered for each layer. The bimetal sheet is meshed by S4R square shell elements with an approximate size of 1 mm, and across the thickness, five Gauss integration points were used. The coefficient of friction between the sheet and the tool and die is considered to be 0.1 mm [20]. The strain path used in the simulation process is two geometries of cone and pyramid with variable wall angles (Fig. 5a). In the simulation process, a spiral tool path (Fig. 5b) and a step-down of 0.5 mm were used [21]. The solver used to perform the simulation process is Dynamic/Explicit. Due to the long solution time of the simulation process, mass scaling 10000 was used to reduce the solution time [22].

3. Results and discussions

In this article, two-layer AL/Mg sheets were manufactured by the roll bonding process. Next, to check the FLD of the two-layer samples, the SPIF was carried out in 2 geometries: pyramid and cone with variable wall angles. Following this, through performing simulation using the ABAQUS Software program, the results obtained from the experimental test and the thickness distribution were checked by the simulation. The FLDs were determined via various approaches (e.g., FLCRT, ESR, SDT, MSR and TSR methods) and were compared with the experiment.

Then, the most accurate method for predicting the failure location and time was evaluated and compared to the experimental method. Thus, the parameters effect of step-down and tool diameter was investigated by numerical simulation method and with the help of DOE on formability value.

3.1. Formability of two-layer sheets in the SPIF process

Formability in forming processes will be defined as the maximum amount of forming until the failure zone [15,16,23]. Nevertheless, in the process of SPIF, the values obtained from formability will be higher than with other conventional methods [24]. The SPIF process was carried out to investigate the formability of the two-layer sheet and to check the effect of geometry and strain path on the FLD. To check the FLD, a circle with a diameter of 2.5 mm with the electrochemical engraving method is done. First, the sample was examined with the arrangement of the Al outer layer (magnesium contacted with the tool). This arrangement is considered to be Mg/Al. The formed samples are shown in Fig. 6 for two pyramid and cone geometries. After the SPIF, investigations were carried out to obtain the fracture depth, forming limit angle, and finally, the FLD study. In Fig. 6 a, the experimental test results related to the two-layer sheet cone geometry with Mg/Al arrangement with a variable angle are observed. As it is known, this sample of the inner layer, a magnesium sheet with a depth of 9 mm and a forming limit angle of 37°, has failed. The same result for pyramid geometry with variable angles, and with 8.5 mm and 35° in-depth and forming limit angle, respectively, can be seen in Fig. 6 b. By examining the fracture area in two-layer samples with Mg/Al arrangement, it can be seen that the magnesium sheet area will crack earlier than the Al layer due to the Mg layer's brittle structure compared to the Al sheet. To investigate the effect of layer arrangement in the two-layer sheet of Mg/Al, the sample with Al/Mg arrangement was prepared for the SPIF process. By examining the results of Fig. 6, it was found that the formability of the cone geometry is more than the pyramid geometry, so the forming test for the Al/Mg arrangement with the cone geometry was investigated (Fig. 7). The fracture depth and the forming limit angle for the Al/Mg arrangement were obtained as 5 mm and 30.5°, respectively, which is less formability than the Mg/Al arrangement. To compare the formability results of the two-layer sheet with Al and magnesium base sheets, the base sheets were formed with the cone geometry. Their results are shown in Fig. 8. For the Al base sheet, depth and forming limit angel of 47.6 mm and 69°, and for the Mg base sheet, depth and forming limit angel of 7.7 mm and 34° were obtained.

To determine FLD, measuring the strains in the sheet is necessary. For this purpose, true strains will be determined by measuring the ellipses' diameters (D_1 , D_2) according to the formulas below.

$$\varepsilon_1 = \ln\left(\frac{D_1}{D_0}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \ln\left(\frac{D_2}{D_0}\right) \quad (3)$$

To evaluate the strain from the FLD, if the combination of strains created during the forming process is below the forming limit curve, the necking condition or failure will not appear, and the forming process will be successful. If the combination of current strains from forming is on the forming limit curve or is placed on top of it, we have reached the situation of necking or failure. After the SPIF process, the FLD will be extracted according to equations (2) and (3). The FLD will be checked in 2 areas of failure and a safe area. These two areas are shown on the FLD according to Fig. 9.

The results obtained from the FLD were summarized for the major and minor strains and are presented in Table 3. Through measuring the strain values created and the SPIF result (Figs. 6 and 9 b) for the cone and pyramid geometries in fracture and safe zones and comparing them with each other, it was found that the strain path in the cone geometry has a higher strain than the pyramid geometry [25]. By examining the FLD results, it is clear that, the strains in the SPIF process are between plane strain and equibiaxial tension [26]. As expected from the forming

Fig. 14. Comparison of failure location prediction with simulation and experimental process,(a) Mg base sheet,(b) Al base sheet,(c) Mg/Al sample (cone),(d) Mg/Al sample (pyramid),(e) Al/Mg sample (cone).

Table 5
Comparison of fracture depth results with experimental and FLD_{crit} simulation methods.

Sample	Depth forming Experimental (mm)	Depth forming simulation (mm)	Error (%)
Mg/Al (Cone)	9	9.9	10
Mg/Al (pyramid)	8.5	7.59	12
Al/Mg (cone)	5	5.65	13
Al base	47.6	43.7	9
Mg base	7.7	8.15	6

Table 6
Comparison of experimental Strain results and numerical simulation methods for base sheets.

Sample	Major Strain (EXP)	Major Strain (SIM)	Error % (Major Strain)	Minor Strain (EXP)	Minor Strain (SIM)	Error % (Minor Strain)
Al base-ESR	0.51	0.55	13.5 %	0.083	0.043	10 %
Al base-TSR		0.7	37 %		0.042	35 %
Al base-MSR		0.76	48 %		0.0145	38 %
Al base-SDT		0.46	12.5 %		0.089	7.6 %
Mg base-ESR	0.11	0.142	27.5 %	0.064	0.054	17.6 %
Mg base-TSR		0.086	30 %		0.051	23 %
Mg base-MSR		0.084	31 %		0.05	27 %
Mg base-SDT		0.138	24 %		0.056	14 %

results, the FLD for the two-layer sample with the outer arrangement of Mg (Fig. 9 c) compared to the outer layer of Al was obtained in lower strain values. This results from lower ductility and the HCP crystalline structure of Mg. By comparing the FLD for base sheet samples and two-layer sheet samples, one can see that the strain of the two-layer sheet with Mg/Al arrangement has decreased by about 51 % compared to the Al base sheet and has increased by about 100 % compared to the Mg base sheet. This indicates that the two-layer sample has better formability than the magnesium base sheet.

3.2. FEM results

3.2.1. Thickness distribution

One of the essential parameters that can be checked in the SPIF process is the thickness distribution value. In forming processes, the lower the thickness reduction compared to the increase of the forming angle, the more suitable the condition of forming process will be. Theoretically, the prediction of the thickness distribution in the simulation process is obtained according to the $\cos \theta$ law ($t_f = \cos \theta \times t_i$) [27]. In the first step, the thickness distribution obtained from the experimental test will be investigated to check the simulation accuracy of two-layer Al/Mg samples in the SPIF process. Since the samples were shaped with variable wall angles, thickness distribution calculations up to the fracture angle will be done for cone and pyramid geometry samples. Thickness distribution for Al and Mg base sheets are shown in Fig. 10. Thickness distribution for the two-layer sample with Mg/Al arrangement with cone and pyramid geometry, respectively, are shown in Figs. 11 and 12. In addition, the results of thickness distribution for Al/Mg layout are shown in Fig. 13. By comparing the results obtained from the experimental and simulation test for thickness distribution, it was found that the results are in good agreement with each other. A summary of the results is given in Table 4. Taking into account that the thickness distribution in the corners of the pyramid geometry is in a more critical condition compared to the wall condition, it can be seen that in this geometry, the thickness in the corners is at its lowest value, which can be one of the reasons for the reduction of the forming limit angle for this geometry relative to the cone geometry (Fig. 12).

3.2.2. Strain distribution

Since in the SPIF process, failure will occur at higher strains [28], the FLD obtained for this process is different from the conventional forming

processes according to the different strain paths [29]. In order to check the strains of fracture areas and predict failure in the SPIF process, five methods were studied: ESR, SDT, TSR, MSR and FLD_{CRT}. In the FLD_{CRT} criteria, the maximum strain a metal sheet can tolerate before necking is considered the formability limit strain [30]. The beginning of necking is expressed according to criterion FLD_{CRT} in the Abaqus software program using condition $\omega_{FLD} = 1$. The ESR criterion is equal to the ratio of the strain rate of the element located in the neck region to the ratio of the effective strain of the element located in the healthy region [31]. In the equation (4) how to calculate ESR is shown. Considering that thinning can be one of the causes of failure in forming processes [32] due to the presence of thickness distribution during the SPIF process, it is necessary to check the prediction of failure through SDT. Based on the SDT model, the thickness of all sheet elements was investigated in finite element simulation, and the elements with minimum thickness were identified. The thinning (thickness strain) of all the elements with the most negligible thickness was stored. Then the second derivative of the thickness strain of these elements was calculated with respect to time [33]. The SDT is defined as equation (5), in which ϵ_{33} is the element thickness strain. MSR is the ratio of the major principal strain rate in the neck region to that of the safe region [34]. The result of this division calculates the necking time for method MSR (equation (6)). TSR is achieved by obtaining the necking time according to equation (7) from dividing the thickness strain in the neck zone by the thickness strain in the safe zone. TSR increases unstably during the necking process. After obtaining the necking time for all the numerical simulation methods, by considering some elements in the neck and safe region according to the obtained necking time, the major and minor strain in the safe and neck region will be obtained. By plotting these points, the FLD will be obtained for each numerical simulation method.

In Fig. 14, the simulation results are shown by the FLD_{CRT} method. The fracture depth obtained for the 2-layers samples and the base sheet was measured as the ω_{FLD} approaches one and compared with the experimental test results. The results are shown in Table 5.

$$ESR = \frac{\text{Effective strain rate in the neck element}}{\text{Effective strain rate in the safe element}} \quad (4)$$

$$\ddot{\epsilon}_{33} = \frac{d^2 \epsilon_{33}}{dt^2} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 15. Numerical simulation method, (a) FLD obtained for Al base sheet, (b) Comparison of major and minor strains in numerical simulation methods.

Fig. 16. Numerical simulation method, (a) FLD obtained for Mg base sheet, (b) Comparison of major and minor strains in numerical simulation methods.

Fig. 17. Numerical simulation method, (a) FLD obtained for Ma/Al (Cone) sheet, (b) Comparison of major and minor strains in numerical simulation methods.

Fig. 18. Numerical simulation method, (a) FLD obtained for Mg/Al (Pyramid) sheet, (b) Comparison of major and minor strains in numerical simulation methods.

Table 7

Comparison of experimental Strain results and numerical simulation methods for 2- layer sheets.

Sample	Major Strain (EXP)	Major Strain (SIM)	Error % (Major Strain)	Minor Strain (EXP)	Minor Strain (SIM)	Error % (Minor Strain)
Mg/Al-ESR (Cone)	0.199	0.156	25 %	0.049	0.04	21 %
Mg/Al-TSR (Cone)		0.148	34 %		0.035	37 %
Mg/Al-MSR (Cone)		0.138	43 %		0.034	42 %
Mg/Al-SDT (Cone)		0.166	20 %		0.04	15 %
Mg/Al-ESR (pyramid)	0.15	0.131	15 %	0.0493	0.042	17 %
Mg/Al-TSR (pyramid)		0.123	21 %		0.036	35 %
Mg/Al-MSR(pyramid)		0.18	21.7 %		0.037	35.8 %
Mg/Al-SDT (pyramid)		0.133	12.7 %		0.043	14 %
Al/Mg-ESR (cone)	0.081	0.072	13.5 %	0.013	0.015	9 %
Al/Mg-TSR (cone)		0.092	28 %		0.017	27.5 %
Al/Mg-MSR (cone)		0.063	28.5 %		0.0186	34 %
Al/Mg-SDT (cone)		0.073	11.2 %		0.0149	7.5 %

Fig. 19. Numerical simulation method, (a) FLD obtained for Al/Mg (Cone) sheet, (b) Comparison of major and minor strains in numerical simulation methods.

Fig. 20. Comparison of FLD results in SPIF and Nakazima method.

Table 8
Design of experiment for SPIF effect parameters on PEEQ.

Experiment NO	Tool Diameter	Step down
1	14	0.2
2	18	1
3	10	0.5
4	14	0.5
5	10	0.2
6	18	0.5
7	14	0.5
8	14	0.5
9	18	0.2
10	14	1
11	14	0.5
12	14	0.5
13	10	1

$$MSR = \frac{\text{Major strain rate in the neck element}}{\text{Major strain rate in the safe element}} \quad (6)$$

$$TSR = \frac{\text{Thickness strain rate in the neck element}}{\text{Thickness strain rate in the safe element}} \quad (7)$$

The numerical methods for the base and two-layer sheets predicted the FLD in the simulation process (see Table 6). Its results are shown in Fig. 15-19. By comparing the results obtained from the FLD_{CRT} and numerical methods; it was observed that the FLD_{CRT} method has a more accurate prediction of the time and place of failure than the ESR, SDT, TSR and MSR methods. The highest error reported for the FLD_{CRT} method (Table 5) was 13 % for a two-layer sheet with Al/Mg arrangement with cone geometry. The Al/Mg arrangement with cone geometry has less formability than the Mg base sheet due to cold work and the increase in the density of dislocations after the rolling process. This result has been confirmed in the simulation of FLD_{CRT} (Table 5) and numerical methods for two-layer sheets (Table 7) (see Fig. 19) (see Fig. 16).

It can be seen the four numerical methods, ESR, SDT, MSR and TSR, that the FLD obtained in the SDT method is more accurate compared to the experimental test (Table 7). One of the reasons why the use of the SPIF process has attracted researchers is that the FLD is higher than in other conventional processes. For validation, the experimental results of the FLD were compared with the experimental results of Rouzbeh et al. [35]. Their study investigated the formability of the two-layer Al/Mg sheet by Nakazima test. The results shown in Fig. 20 confirm the increase of the FLD in the SPIF process compared to other forming methods [36].

4. Design of experiments

After validating the simulation results and continuing to obtain the most accurate method (STD) in predicting the FLD diagram, the effect of

Table 9
Variance analysis for the effect of step down and tool diameter on PEEQ of Mg/Al Pyramid.

Source	DF	F-Value	P-Value
Model	5	70.49	0.000
Linear	2	90.25	0.000
step down	1	172.17	0.000
Tool diameter	1	8.32	0.023
Square	2	80.46	0.000
step down*step down	1	14.50	0.007
Tool diameter*Tool diameter	1	159.88	0.000
2-Way Interaction	1	0.03	0.864
step down*Tool diameter	1	0.03	0.864
Error	7		
Lack-of-Fit	3		
Pure Error	4		
Total	12		

step down and tool diameter on the formability of Mg/Al pyramid samples was performed through the simulation process. The DOE by Minitab software with the RSM, according to Table 8, was done. In the analysis of variance, if the p-value is less than 0.05, it indicates that the assumption that the parameters have an effect on formability, is correct [37]. By checking Table 9, it can be seen that for both the parameters of the step-down and tool diameter, the p-value is less than 0.05 [38]. The parameters were investigated in a constant strain path for the equivalent strain equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) [39]. By evaluating Fig. 21, it can be seen that the formability decreases with the increase of the step down [40]. Due to the reduction of the local stresses created in the location of the tool movement path, the formability decreases with the step-down increases [41]. Nevertheless, there is an optimal value for the tool diameter. The optimal value for the tool diameter has been obtained at 15.17 mm (see Fig. 20-c). In fact, when the tool diameter increases, the contact area between the tool and the sheet increases. As a result, the tensile and shear stress of the sheet and the contact area of the tool and sheet have increased, which will increase thinning and failure [42].

5. Conclusions

- (1) By carrying out the experimental SPIF test for Al and Mg base sheet samples and two-layer samples, it was determined that the formability of the two-layer sheet with two cone and pyramid geometries with Al/Mg arrangement has increased by about 16 % compared to the Mg base sheet.
- (2) The cone geometry has higher formability in the two-layer samples than the pyramid geometry. Furthermore, the formability of the Mg/Al arrangement is about 80 % higher than the Al/Mg arrangement.
- (3) Investigation of the thickness distribution for base sheet samples and two-layer samples was carried out experimentally and by simulation, and the results were in good agreement with a margin of error of less than 10 %.
- (4) Failure prediction was made using the simulation process with FLD_{crt} and ESR methods, and the results were compared with the experimental tests. The results showed that the numerical-experimental FLD_{crt} method has a higher accuracy for failure prediction.
- (5) By comparing two numerical methods, ESR and SDT compared, to the experimental method, it was found that the SDT method is more accurate than the ESR.
- (6) Comparing the results of the FLD test in the SPIF process and the Nakazima test shows that the formability is higher in the SPIF process.
- (7) The parameters effect of step down and tool diameter was investigated by SDT numerical method by DOE for two-layer Mg/Al pyramid sheets and the results showed that there is an optimal

Fig. 21. DOE for Mg/Al sample, a) surface plot, b) contour plot, c) Response optimization.

value for tool diameter, but step down has an inverse relationship with formability.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work is based upon research funded by Iran national science foundation (INSF) under project No, 4005147.

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